

MIXED MODE FRACTURE ENERGY OF FIBRE/MATRIX INTERFACE- A COUPLED EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL STUDY

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1 Introduction

It is well established that the microscale properties of composites strongly affect their macroscopic behaviour. In order to be able to understand the macroscopic behaviour of composites, detailed characterisation of the microscale properties is required. The properties of all composite materials constituents should be characterized, including fibre/matrix interface which plays a key role in the load transfer. It has been found that e.g. macroscale transverse cracks in fibre composites are caused by the coalescence of the interfacial fibre/matrix debonding [1].

Having characterized the relevant microscale mechanical properties including interface properties, overall mechanical properties can be predicted by micromechanical modelling. Moreover, a direct link between the microscopic properties with the macroscopic composite behaviour can be established. Therefore, an understanding and control of the interface properties is of high importance. Thus, the studies of the fibre/matrix interface cracking received considerable attention.

Fibre/matrix debonding is essentially mixed mode interface cracking. In order to investigate debonding initiation and propagation a single fibre specimen subjected to a transverse load has been studied in the literature. The problem is schematically shown in Fig.1. The fibre/matrix interfacial debonding has been studied mainly using Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics (LEFM) approach. Toya [2], deduced the analytical solution of the energy release rate as a function of the debond angle for a circular inclusion embedded in infinite solid. The same approach was applied in numerical simulations elsewhere [3]. It was found that the debonding propagates unstably starting from $\theta_d = 0^\circ$ to the angle of $\theta_d = 60^\circ - 70^\circ$ under mixed mode conditions, dominated by Mode I for debond angles smaller than 30° (nomenclature

according to Fig.1). Subsequently, the growth of the interfacial crack is stable in pure Mode II or the interfacial crack kinks out into the matrix. Elsewhere, the fibre/matrix interface debonding was studied by mixed mode cohesive approach [4]. All numerical predictions available in the literature were compared with experimental observations obtained by optical microscopy [3,4]. However, these observations do not allow for the precise debonding angle measurements. As mentioned, the interfacial crack occurs under mixed mode conditions. The debonding initiation is predominantly normal opening (Mode I). Subsequently, the crack is under mixed-mode conditions and mode-mixity evolves with the debond angle growth (contribution of a shear opening increases).

It is well established that for the interfaces bonding dissimilar materials the Mode II fracture energy, Γ_{II} is several times larger than energy Mode I, Γ_I [5-7]. Therefore, the fracture energy of the fibre/matrix interface must be determined for mixed mode conditions.

It should be noticed, that a single fibre specimen is only the first step in revealing a transverse crack nucleation in fibre composites. Once the interface parameters have been determined using a single fibre composite, the next step is to simulate a real composite microstructure that includes defects and a number of fibres to predict debonding, interfacial cracks kinking into the matrix, their subsequent coalescence leading to the transverse macro crack nucleation.

The current studies present a coupled experimental and numerical approach for fibre/matrix interface fracture parameters determination. An augmented finite element method (A-FEM) [8] has been used for numerical simulations and *in situ* fracture tests of a single-fibre specimen were conducted in the chamber of scanning electron microscope (SEM).

High resolution SEM micrographs allowed for debonding observations *in situ*. The debond angles and the debond opening displacements are measured as functions of the applied stress. By the comparison of experimental and numerical results micromechanical modelling parameters are identified. Cohesive law parameters are estimated and Mode I fracture energy is determined

2 Experimental method

A transverse tensile load was applied to a single fibre specimen as shown schematically in Fig.1. The sample is made of a thick glass fibre with diameter of $\sim 50\mu\text{m}$ which is embedded in the epoxy resin. The fibres are pre-strained before casting in the resin in order to minimize the residual stress. The pre-straining procedure is carried out according to the method available in the literature [9]. The sample was dog-bone shaped and polished in order to remove any microcracks and to allow for microscopy observations. The surfaces to be observed in SEM were coated with the carbon coat to prevent charging of the non-conductive polymer. The geometry of the sample which was used in *in situ* tests is shown in Fig.2. The tensile tests were conducted in the chamber of SEM by applying a tensile load in x -direction (see Fig.2). A special load rig was used (see Fig.3). The load was applied in increments and the sample was partly unloaded after each increment to avoid any creeping during scanning time. The step-wise loading is shown schematically in Fig.4 where $\bar{\sigma}_{xx}$ is the applied stress. An acoustic emission (AE) sensor was mounted on the sample to assist the detection of the damage initiation/propagation.

3 Experimental results

The debonding initiation and propagation were successfully observed during *in situ* tests in SEM. An example of observed damage sequence is shown in Fig.5. Two characteristic features, the debonding angle, θ_d and the normal opening, Δ_n (see Fig. 1) were measured after each load step. However, in some cases due to the poor micrographs quality the debonding was not visible and no data was obtained. Since the problem is symmetrical along x -plane, two debond angles can be measured as indicated in Fig.1. The measured values as functions of applied stress are presented in Fig.6. The debonding propagated unstably right after its initiation and the first debond arrest was observed when the debond angle reached $\theta_d \sim 40^\circ\text{-}60^\circ$ at the stress level of

$\bar{\sigma}_{xx} = 3\text{-}5\text{MPa}$ (see Fig.5 and 6). At subsequent stress levels the debond angle propagated and the normal opening evolved as seen in Fig.5 and Fig.6. At the average stress level of $\bar{\sigma}_{xx} \sim 13\text{MPa}$ the interfacial crack kinked out of the fibre/matrix interface into the matrix as seen in Fig.5c. The debond angle corresponding to kinking initiation is found to be in the interval of $\theta_d = 60^\circ \pm 14^\circ$.

3 Micromechanical modelling

A unit cell model consisting of $2 \times 2\text{mm}$ matrix domain which includes the fibre with diameter of $\sim 50\mu\text{m}$ was implemented in ABAQUS 6.12 through user-defined elements. Although, the problem is symmetric and in principle a quarter of the fibre with the surrounding matrix could be considered (symmetry along x and y plane, see Fig.1), for the studies of symmetry of the problem and capacity of the numerical method, the entire fibre is considered in the numerical simulations. The entire model was meshed with 4-nodal elements. Since no significant evidence of matrix plasticity was observed in the *in situ* tests, elasticity was assumed for both, the matrix and the fibre domains. The Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio for the fibre are $E_f = 70\text{GPa}$, $\nu_f = 0.21$ and those for the matrix are $E_m = 4\text{GPa}$, $\nu_f = 0.3$. The matrix's parameters are based on the data provided by the manufacturer of the epoxy resin used in the experiments. The fibre parameters are set close to the data found in the literature [3]. A-FEM was utilized for numerical simulations of fibre/matrix interfacial debonding [8,10]. The A-FEM does not need to model the fibre/matrix interface explicitly as a single layer of cohesive elements. The interface is embedded into the ring of solid elements containing the fibre/matrix interface as shown in Fig.7. That is, all these elements have two materials domain. As load increases, the debonding will initiate along the interface when the critical interface stresses are reached [10]. The triangular mixed mode traction-separation law was used for interfacial debonding simulations (Fig.8). The Mode I and Mode II traction-separation laws are only coupled by a failure criterion [11]:

$$G_I / \Gamma_I + G_{II} / \Gamma_{II} = 1 \quad (1)$$

where, Γ_I and Γ_{II} are Mode I and Mode II fracture energy respectively, represented by the total areas

given by the traction-separations curves for each mode (Fig.8).

In the failure criteria described by Equation (1), G_I , G_{II} represent Mode I and Mode II work of the cohesive tractions given by

$$G_I = \int_0^{\delta_n} \sigma(\delta_n) d\delta_n \quad (2)$$

$$G_{II} = \int_0^{\delta_t} \sigma(\delta_t) d\delta_t \quad (3)$$

where δ_n and δ_t are normal and tangential displacement respectively, $\hat{\sigma}$, $\hat{\tau}$ are the peak normal and shear tractions, δ_{nc} and δ_{tc} are the critical normal and tangential displacements and δ_{n1} and δ_{t1} are the separations at which the peak normal and shear traction values are reached.

4 Coupled experimental and numerical study

The cohesive law parameters can be estimated by coupled experimental and numerical approach. Two parameters from numerical and experimental results are compared: interface debonding angle, θ_d and normal opening, Δ_n after the debonding crack is arrested (Fig.1). Firstly, Mode I parameters are determined by using experimental results as follows. It is recognized, that the debonding initiation at $\theta_d=0^\circ$ is nearly Mode I opening [2]. Therefore, the Mode I cohesive strength is deduced by the stress analyses at this location at the applied nominal stress of $\bar{\sigma}_{xx}=3-5MPa$ which caused debonding initiation in the experimental observations. The contour plot for the stress analyses which was made using continuum elements of ABAQUS is shown in Fig.9. It was found that the normal stress at the location of the debonding initiation ($\theta_d=0^\circ$) is ~ 1.5 times higher than the far field nominal stress. Thereby, the cohesive strength for fracture Mode I is found to be in the range of $\hat{\sigma}=4.5-7.5MPa$.

Critical opening for Mode I cohesive law is also deduced from the experimental results. It is found that the normal opening at the initiation stage is $\Delta_n \sim 0.17\mu m$. It can be therefore deduced, that the critical opening of the Mode I cohesive law must be $\delta_{nc} < 0.17\mu m$.

Having deduced critical normal opening and the cohesive strength, several numerical simulations were run in order to find the Mode I fracture energy of the interface which allows obtaining the debonding initiation at the nominal stress of $\bar{\sigma}_{xx}=3-5MPa$ as it was observed in the

experiments. In the numerical simulations the cohesive strength was fixed and the critical normal opening and shear opening were adjusted. It is noted that for many interfaces, the Mode II fracture energy, Γ_{II} has been found to be several times larger than fracture energy Mode I, Γ_I [5-7]. Therefore, in the present study the fracture energy for Mode II over Mode I was chosen to be $\Gamma_{II}/\Gamma_I = 4$. All parameters for the cohesive laws used in this study are in Table 1.

5 Numerical results

The debond angle which was detected following the failure criteria from equation 1 is measured at each increment and so is the normal opening. The measured values are plotted as functions of applied stress in Fig.10a and Fig.10b. Since the numerically predicted debonding angles distinguished in Fig.1 as θ_{dI} and θ_{dII} , developed fairly symmetrically, the debond angle in Fig.10a is an averaged one, i.e., $\theta_d = (\theta_{dI} + \theta_{dII})/2$. In all cases the debonding occurs and propagates unstably and the first debond arrest is observed at the angle of $\theta_d = 30^\circ - 45^\circ$. The unstable debond propagation is in good agreement with experimental observations. The debonding initiation occurs at the stress level determined in the experiments for simulations whose cohesive critical displacement is in the range of $\delta_{nc} = 0.03 - 0.04\mu m$. However, the debond angles at the subsequent stress levels are slightly larger than those observed in the experiments (see Fig.6 for comparison and cohesive law parameters in Table.1). For larger critical displacement, the debonding angles at higher stress levels are in better agreement with experimental observations, although the debonding initiation in these cases requires higher stress level (see Fig.6 for comparison and Table.1 for cohesive law parameters). The fracture energy for Mode I and Mode II can be found as $\Gamma_I = \hat{\sigma}\delta_{nc}/2$ and $\Gamma_{II} = \hat{\sigma}\delta_{tc}/2$, respectively. Thus, from Fig. 10a, it appears that the interface toughness Mode I is in the range of $\Gamma_I = 0.1 - 0.25J/m^2$.

The normal opening (Δ_n) is also plotted as a function of applied stress and the 'stretching' of the interface observed before complete debonding occurs is included in Fig.10b. It can be seen that the debonding initiation occurs when the critical normal opening has been reached. All curves show a distinctive transition from an unstable phase (rapid increase of Δ_n with $\bar{\sigma}_{xx}$) to a stable phase (more

gradual increase of Δ_n). The transition point Therefore, only in case of cohesive critical opening being in the range of $\delta_{nc} < 0.2\mu m$, the debonding initiation occurs in the desired nominal stress of $\bar{\sigma}_{xx} = 3-5MPa$ determined in the experimental testing. The critical normal opening displacement obtained in the numerical simulations where the fracture energy is in the range of $\Gamma_I \sim 0.1J/m^2$ are similar to the normal openings measured in SEM micrographs. For the fracture energy which is higher than $0.1J/m^2$, the normal openings are slightly smaller than experimental ones shown in Fig.6. All simulations are completed very fast in comparison with non-linear analysis conducted by standard FEM method.

6 Summary and conclusions

A new *in situ* method for debonding observations of fibre/matrix interface debonding is proposed. The sample manufacturing procedure allowed for obtaining a proper fibre/matrix bonding and removing all microcraks. The high resolution SEM images allowed for the *in situ* observations of the debonding process. By comparing the experimental measurements of debond angle and debond normal opening with numerical results obtained using A-FEM the Mode I fracture energy of the interface is found to be $\sim 0.1J/m^2$. The Mode I cohesive law parameters are identified by a coupled experimental and numerical approach. The cohesive strength is determined to be in the level of $\hat{\sigma} = 4.5-7.5MPa$ and normal critical opening is found to be $\delta_{nc} < 0.2\mu m$. The fracture energy and the cohesive law parameters for fracture Mode II can be estimated by the parametric study which compares the debond angle and normal opening evolution from the experiments with numerical predictions. In the present study, the ratio of fracture energy for Mode II over Mode I was chosen to be 4. The debond angles obtained in the numerical predictions are slightly higher than those measured experimentally. Therefore, more parametric studies should be conducted in order to identify the interface parameters for fracture Mode II. It is expected, that the higher ratio of the fracture energies, Γ_{II} / Γ_I would results in smaller debond angles for subsequent stress levels and thereby, in better agreement with experimentally measured debond angles.

A-FEM is shown to be suitable for the cohesive zone modelling of the microscale problems.

In the future work the kinking phenomenon observed in the experiments should be included in the numerical simulations. Since the numerical method is found to be time efficient in the cohesive-zone simulations, it is expected that it will be competitive for standard methods like e.g. X-FEM for kinking problem simulations.

Fig.1. Single- fibre model composite under transverse load.

Fig.2. Sample geometry used in the *in situ* tests in SEM.

Fig. 3. Test set up for *in situ* SEM observations.

Fig.4. Step wise loading during *in situ* testing.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 5. Fibre/matrix interface: (a) undamaged interface, (b) interfacial debonding initiation, (c) interfacial crack kinking into the matrix

(a)

(b)

Fig. 6. Experimental results presented as functions of applied stress, (a) debond angle and (b) normal opening

Fig. 7. Fibre/matrix interface represented by solid elements.

Mode II (Γ_{II})

Fig. 8. Mixed-mode cohesive traction-separation laws used in this study.

Fig. 9. Stress analyses for estimation of the cohesive strength Mode I; contour plot of local normal stress for the nominal stress $\bar{\sigma}_{xx} \sim 5MPa$.

Table 1. Cohesive parameters used in the numerical simulations

$\hat{\sigma} = \hat{\tau}$ [MPa]	δ_{nc} [μm]	δ_{tc} [μm]	$\delta_{tc} / \delta_{nc}$ [-]	Γ_I [J/m^2]
5	0.03	0.12	4	0.075
5	0.04	0.16	4	0.1
5	0.1	0.4	4	0.25
5	0.2	0.8	4	0.5

(a)

(b)

Fig. 10. Numerical results for different fracture energy, (a) debond angle as a function of applied stress and (b) normal opening as applied stress.

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